

D16.2 – Final report on the ARIADNEplus pilots

Version 1 (*final*)

02/12/22

Grant Agreement number: 823914

Project acronym: ARIADNEplus

Project title: Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe - plus

Funding Scheme: H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1

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The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Programme (H2020-INFRAIA-2018-1) under grant agreement n° 823914.

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Document History

- 10.11.2022– Draft Version 0.1
- 30.11.2022 – Draft Version 0.2
- 01.02.2022 – Quality Control

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the activities carried out during the ARIADNEplus project within Work Package 16 (WP16) by the different partners and describes the results achieved.

WP16 - Innovative Methods and Pilots concerns the preparation of pilots, i.e., exemplary applications of the ARIADNEplus services to be used as demonstrators of the potential of the ARIADNEplus framework. They address specific archaeological research questions and use one or more of the ARIADNEplus services operating on a selected data sample. The list of such pilots and the corresponding WP tasks is provided below. Partners involved are also listed, with the Task leader in bold.

Task 16.1 – Establishing a common framework for the ARIADNEplus pilots. Partners involved: **CYI**, SRFG, INRAP.

Task 16.2 – ARIADNEplus for Airborne-LiDAR data use and reuse. Partners involved: **ZRC-SAZU**, CARARE, CNR-ISTI(VCL).

Task 16.3 – ARIADNEplus for a Historic Environment Spatial Data Infrastructure. Partners involved: **CARARE**, ZRC-SAZU, other ARIADNEplus partners as required.

Task 16.4 – ARIADNEplus for sharing archaeology in 3D. Partners involved: **CYI**, CNR-ISTI(VCL).

Task 16.5 – ARIADNEplus for public/community archaeology. Partners involved: **AU**, UoY-ADS, DANS-KNAW, BUP-DMS, UH.

Task 16.6 – ARIADNEplus for understanding ancient and present cities: scanning the heart of Rome. Partners involved: **MIBACT-ICCU (ICA)**, CNR-ISTI(VCL).

Task 16.7 – Exploiting the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure to understand complex phenomena of the Past. Partners involved: **UB**, PIN.

Task 16.8 – ARIADNEplus for Preventive Archaeology. Partners involved: **INRAP**, UoY- ADS, USW.

The report starts with a brief introduction to the WP goals and each pilot is described in a specific section, which details the archaeological issue addressed, including the necessary background; the perspective target users; the data to be used; the pilot results and the deviation from the work plan, if any.

2 Introduction and Objectives

The present deliverable reports the results achieved by ARIADNEplus in the preparation of pilots within WP16. The pilots are exemplary applications of the ARIADNEplus services to specific archaeological research questions, aiming at:

- Defining the innovative methods enabled by ARIADNEplus services for archaeological research communities;
- Testing the services and innovative methods on real use cases through the pilots;
- Demonstrating the advantages of using ARIADNEplus to the archaeological user communities;
- Showcasing the ARIADNEplus data and services for building applications for professionals, heritage managers and the public at large.

The project planned to develop seven pilots, so the WP consists of a coordination task (T16.1), aimed at defining a common framework to design and present the pilots, and seven tasks (T16.2 to T16.8) corresponding to the individual pilots.

As already mentioned, the pilots aimed at demonstrating the ARIADNEplus services in real applications. Developing the pilots heavily depended on the availability of the services and developments, but the pilot design also influenced the way services were designed.

Throughout the project, the WP pilots held intensive discussions which brought the perspective of archaeological users to the project. This mechanism allowed the services and all the actors of the project to be fed with the needs and expectations of this community.

To present the final results of the work package, an online workshop was organized on October 12th, 2022. All task leaders attended the workshop, coordinated by the WP leader Kai Salas Rossenbach. They reported about the final results of their pilot. The discussion mainly focused and the ways of disseminating inside and outside ARIADNE network the results of these experiments.

Figure 1. A snapshot of the WP 16 final workshop held online on 12/10/2022.

3 Task 16.1 - Establishing a common framework for the ARIADNEplus pilots

3.1 Task description

As previously stated, Task 16.1 was in charge of the harmonization of the Pilots deployment, establishing a common framework in which they are developed as regards the engagement and mobilisation of the targeted communities, and the description of lessons learned from them. The Task produced a form to monitor regularly the progress, shown below.

Work Package 16: Innovative Methods and Pilots

Pilot description template

Pilot title:

Proposed by: *[should be partners who would run the pilot, at least 2 partners]*

- [Partner]
- [Partner]
- [Partner]

Brief description:

Description [max. 10 lines]

ARIADNEplus service/s to be used:

[at least one ARIADNEplus service must be used, but not too many; also mention if (a) newly developed in ARIADNEplus or (b) already available and planned to be enhanced; also mention key requirements with regard to implementation and/or use by target group/s]

- Service [newly developed in ARIADNEplus /or/ already available and planned to be enhanced]
- Service [newly developed in ARIADNEplus /or/ already available and planned to be enhanced]

Key requirements:

ARIADNEplus data to be (re-)used:

[at least 1 dataset or collection (better more) registered in A+ must be used (otherwise there would be a too weak relation with A+); in addition also one or more external would be good to include, mobilized for inclusion in A+ or linked through Linked Data; also mention key requirements for data (re-)use, e.g. data/set formats, vocabularies, license, ...]

- Data set/collection:
- Data set/collection:

Key requirements:

External target group/s of the pilot:

[avoid "General public" and address specific target groups, i.e. providers/re-users of scientific data; museums, etc. with a clear potential for uptake]

Target group type (e.g.):

- Researchers in *[mention domain/s, i.e. art & architecture, bioarchaeology, ...]*
- Research data managers in *[mention domain/s, if relevant]*
- CH management, CH practitioners (i.e. museums), ...
- Businesses, i.e. creative industry, tourism, ...
- Citizen scientists
- Other specific target group

Size (estimate):

Knowledge/skills required by target group for uptake:

Other group characteristics relevant for the pilot:

Figure 2. The template for pilot data collection (page 1)

Related projects: Project, type of relation Project, type of relation
External organisation or projects involved: Organisation; kind of support Organisation; kind of support
ARIADNEplus promotion of the pilot: <i>[consider specific activities beyond the general stream of project communication/dissemination]</i> Promotion through...
References: <i>[add references and links for organisations, projects, resources mentioned in the pilot description]</i>
Notes <i>[Put here any other relevant information or explanation]</i>

Figure 3. The template for pilot data collection (page 2)

The details of each report, integrated by the workshop presentation, are described in the following sections, each one dedicated to a task.

The relationship between pilots and services are summarized in the table below.

Task	Title	Main related service(s)
T16.2	ARIADNEplus for airborne-LiDAR data use and reuse	Cloud geo-server (T15.7) Visual services (T15.1)
T16.3	ARIADNEplus for a historic environment spatial data Infrastructure	Cloud geo-server (T15.7)
T16.4	ARIADNEplus for sharing archaeology in 3D	Visual services (T15.1)
T16.5	ARIADNEplus for public/community archaeology	Query services (T15.5) Visual services (T15.1)
T16.6	ARIADNEplus for understanding ancient and present cities: scanning the heart of Rome	Cloud geo-server (T15.7)
T16.7	Exploiting the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure to understand complex phenomena of the Past	Cloud geo-server (T15.7) Application profile for inscriptions (T4.4.13 and T14.2)
T16.8	ARIADNEplus for Preventive archaeology	Text mining & NLP (T15.4)

Table 1 – Main services used in pilots

3.2 Deviation from work plan

No substantial deviation from the work plan.

4 Task 16.2- ARIADNEplus for Airborne-LiDAR data use and reuse

4.1 Pilot description

Airborne-LiDAR data are usually encoded as very high-resolution images, where pixels represent the height of the terrain represented; to be suitable for archaeological interpretation they need a customized interface to provide visualization functionalities which should go beyond usual image visualization. This task identifies suitable re-useable A-LiDAR data in the ARIADNEplus content pool and disseminates it through ARIADNEplus Visual Media Service (VMS) – an extension of the existing High-resolution images VMS component.

Data-contributors are specialists in the field that currently don't have a suitable tool for dissemination (traditional articles are not a proper vehicle for the dissemination and analysis of those data). Data-users are other interested researchers, e.g., A-LiDAR- specialists or archaeologists interested in specific topics (e.g., Iron Age hillforts) or areas. They contribute expertise (e.g., archaeological analogy) and/or skills and tools (e.g., proprietary software) for creative enhancement of the content. Data-users can explore (online, using VMS) and re-use (offline, VMS allows data download) the data. Re-use is primarily focused either on metadata (creating additional archaeological interpretation) or data (processing enhancement). Data-contributors gain scientific recognition (CC-BY) and possibly enhanced data. Data-users gain access to processed airborne LiDAR data and archaeological data.

The task will target groups such as researchers working with A-LiDAR data willing to make it available under an open data licence and archaeologists specialized in particular subjects (e.g., Iron Age) and/or regions (e.g., eastern Alps). It is the aim of this service to provide tools for non-LiDAR specialists to fully benefit from the A-LiDAR data; other beneficiaries will be specialists from various scientific fields, industries and governmental institutions outside of archaeology and cultural heritage that are using LiDAR data (e.g., geographers, geologists, forestry industry, etc.).

4.2 Specific objectives

Specific objectives of task 16.2 were:

- to demonstrate a customised interface, which will provide visualisation functionalities;
- to identify suitable re-useable LiDAR data in the ARIADNEplus content pool and disseminates it through ARIADNEplus Visual Media Service (VMS);
- to provide tools for non-LiDAR specialists to fully benefit from the LiDAR data.

4.3 Perspective users and pilot dissemination

Perspective users of the task 16.2 are:

- Archaeologists;
- Archaeologists working with remote sensing data;
- Researchers working with airborne LiDAR;
- Research data managers in remote sensing;

- CH management and CH practitioners working with/in landscape;
- Businesses working with airborne LiDAR data.

Pilot is disseminated through the final report for the task 16.2, which includes the demonstrator. The final report has been deposited within the VRE ARIADNEplus_project that is running on the D4Science platform. The demonstrator is available here: <https://data.d4science.net/Vd5g>.

4.4 ARIADNEplus service tested

For the purposes of the task 16.2 we have tested the following services:

- D4Science, VRE "GeoNa Prototype", available at <https://ariadne.d4science.org/web/geona-prototype>);
- GIS Cloud (<https://www.giscloud.com>);
- ArcGIS Apps (<https://www.arcgis.com>).

4.5 Data used for the pilot

For the task 16.2 we have utilised the following datasets:

- Airborne LiDAR-derived DFMs and interpretative mapping of archaeological data;
- *.tiff: GeoTIFF (4 x 25 MB);
- *tpk: Raster Layer Packages (4 x 100MB);
- *shp: Vector layers (2 x 1MB).

All data are scientific derivatives of source data, that is distributed as a CC0-equivalent. The data is distributed through the demonstrator (available here: <https://data.d4science.net/Vd5g>).

4.6 Description of the methodology of the test and results

The methodology of the task 16.2 had the following steps:

1. Scientific process
 - a. LiDAR data processing
 - b. interpretative mapping of archaeological features
 - c. writing the scientific report
2. Testing available services
 - d. D4Science
 - e. GIS Cloud
 - f. ArcGIS Instant App
2. Developing the pilot:
 - a. packaging raster layers and all referenced data sources to create a single compressed layer package
 - b. creating WMS
 - c. designing ArcGIS Instant App
 - d. designing the pilot publication

The methodology is described in more detail in the final report of the task available here <https://data.d4science.net/Vd5g>.

4.7 VRE of the pilot

The ARIADNEplus_project VRE is running on the D4Science platform. The demonstrator is available here: <https://data.d4science.net/Vd5g>.

4.8 Added value of ARIADNEplus for the pilot/theme and for the end user

Added value of ARIADNEplus for the pilot:

- ARIADNEplus provided stimulating environment

Added value of the pilot for the end user:

- demonstration of a customised interface
- identified suitable re-useable LiDAR data in the ARIADNEplus content

4.9 Deviation from work plan

There were no deviations from the work plan.

5 Task 16.3 - ARIADNEplus for a Historic Environment Spatial Data Infrastructure

5.1 Pilot description

The pilot aimed to test and explore the potential for publishing, sharing and reusing archaeological geospatial datasets within Spatial Data Infrastructures (SDIs) frameworks. A Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) is defined “as a framework of policies, institutional arrangements, technologies, data, and people that enables the sharing and effective usage of geographic information”¹. In effect this results in a series of protocols, software and services which enable the effective publishing and reuse of geospatial data.

Several key benefits and outcomes are generated through the development and establishment of SDIs, including:

- reducing duplication of efforts amongst data providers;
- decreasing the cost of geospatial data;
- Improving accessibility to geospatial data;
- Improving the benefits of utilising pre-existing spatial data;
- Increasing the sharing and harmonisation of spatial data between and across domains and geographic regions including government, research/academia and the private sector.

Within archaeology and the wider historic environment sector, the ability to create and consume geospatial data is great. Field practices such as excavation, survey, geophysical prospection generate vast quantities of important spatial data, which is often flattened into the form of an illustrative image and removed from future analysis and reuse. By using the power of established SDI components, the effort and costs in capturing this important data can hopefully be realised through reuse and analysis.

The pilot attempts to demonstrate some of the ambitions behind the development of an SDI for the historic environment as laid out in the published paper “One Archaeology: A Manifesto for the Systematic and Effective Use of Mapped Data from Archaeological Fieldwork and Research”², which proposes the formalised management of primary research data through an archaeological Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) and builds upon the already established reuses of geospatial data within the EU INSPIRE Directive. Through the development of an SDI for the historic environment, several beneficial outcomes could present themselves, including:

- The ability to collate and share data between users within the historic environment sector and beyond to enable effective research using primary data;

¹ “Tonchovska, Rumyana; Stanley, Victoria; De Martino, Samantha. 2012. Spatial Data Infrastructure and INSPIRE. Europe and Central Asia knowledge brief; issue no. 55. World Bank, Washington, DC. © World Bank. <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/17082> License: CC BY 3.0 IGO.”

² McKeague, P.; Corns, A.; Larsson, Å.; Moreau, A.; Posluschny, A.; Van Daele, K.; Evans, T. One Archaeology: A Manifesto for the Systematic and Effective Use of Mapped Data from Archaeological Fieldwork and Research. *Information* 2020, **11**, 222. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info11040222>

- Improving the use of archaeological spatial data in aspects of digital transformation, including informed policy development through the analysis of geospatial data.

The proposition of developing a fully integrated SDI for the historic environment is beyond this pilot, however key integral components can be showcased here with the aim of developing them further in the future with European partners. The pilot aimed to explore two components of an SDI infrastructure:

1. The use of geospatial services in the publishing and reuse of geospatial data, including Web mapping Services (WMS), Web Feature Services (WFS) and Web Coverage Services (WCS)
2. The implementation and publication of geospatial cataloguing service to harvest and publish access to historic environment data which exists across the European region thus enabling and promoting reuse of this geospatial data.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of the main components within a Spatial Data Infrastructure

5.2 Specific objectives

Two specific objectives were established during the lifetime of the project:

Objective 1: Establish a geospatial portal and cataloguing application, which could provide the following functions to both users and data providers:

1. User objectives
 - a. Provision of web interface to search and explore existing geospatial data across a range of catalogues;
 - b. Geospatial and faceted search functions based upon several factors, including data publishers, scales, data types/formats and data themes;
 - c. Where applicable, enable user to preview geospatial data available in the catalogue.
2. Data publisher/administration objectives

- a. The ability to schedule the harvest of metadata from multiple sources including OGC-CSW 2.0.2 ISO Profile, OAI-PMH, Z39.50 and additional protocols/standards;
 - b. The ability to ingest geospatial metadata records for the population of the catalogue.
3. Cataloguing objective
- a. Identify relevant available geospatial services, which could be utilised within the research and analysis of the historic environment. Due to the limited scope of this pilot, this will not be achieved for all geographic regions and data suppliers in Europe, so effort was focused on partners who could provide relevant services or on those geographic regions where a large amount of data would be readily available to highlight the benefits of further effort in constructing the catalogue.

Objective 2: Establish a geospatial webserver for the publication of demonstration geospatial services for a range of historic environment datasets including landscape data and remote sensing data (geophysics and ALS).

The GeoServer functionality should include the ability to publish and access the following geospatial services:

- a. Web Map Service (WMS) Interface Standard³ for the publication of digital image files or maps derived from a range of geospatial data. This mapping service is suitable for basic mapping, where attribution of data is not required or particularly appropriate for data such as scanned maps, orthoimagery and other image-based raster datasets.
- b. Web Feature Services (WFS) Interface Standard⁴ for the publication of vector based geospatial data with associated attribution. Within the scope of this pilot, only Simple WFS services will be created which have the following operations: GetCapabilities, DescribeFeatureType, ListStoredQueries, DescribeStoredQueries, GetFeature operation with only the StoredQuery action. No data editing/creation/deletion operations as displayed with Transaction WFS will be created.
- c. Web Coverage Service (WCS) Interface Standard⁵ for the publication of geospatial data representing space/time-varying phenomena, specifically spatio-temporal regular and irregular grids (e.g., DEM raster datasets), point clouds, and general meshes.

³ OpenGIS® Web Map Server Implementation Specification. 2006. Available online https://portal.ogc.org/files/?artifact_id=14416

⁴ OGC® Web Feature Service 2.0 Interface Standard – With Corrigendum, 2014. Available online <http://www.opengis.net/doc/IS/wfs/2.0.2>

⁵ OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS) 2.1 Interface Standard – Core, 2018. Available at <http://www.opengis.net/doc/IS/wcs-core/2.1>

Service Type	Example of suitable historic environment data	Benefits of service choice
Web Map Service (WMS)	Image based spatial data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Background mapping • Scanned Historical Maps • Orthoimagery • Rectified aerial imagery • Basic hillshade data 	Data is rendered quickly Good for production of simple maps Maintain cartographic style when data is published
Web Feature Services (WFS)	Vector-based spatial data with associated attribution data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey extents • Individual point data e.g., site/artefact/event data • Transcription/interpretation of archaeological objects e.g., site surveys, excavation digitisation, transcription 	Users can carry out advanced queries to retrieve attribute information
Web Coverage Service (WCS)	Multidimensional thematic raster data where the cells can be interrogated or displayed based upon their value <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topography data (DEM) • Geophysical survey data • Satellite imagery • Soil data 	Ability to represent multidimensional data formats Ability to handle temporal/multi-year data Ability to analyse and query raster data

Table 2. Archaeological examples of the relevant data which can be published through the different envisaged services as part of the ARIADNEplus Pilot

5.3 Perspective users and pilot dissemination

There is a large number of potential users who would benefit from the full development of the services within this ARIADNEplus pilot. Users both within and external to the archaeology community would benefit through greater access to authoritative, rich and current archaeological geospatial data, which helps users understand the rich nature of the historic environment. Conversely, archaeological users would benefit from exposure and access to geospatial data from outside of their core domain, such as environmental geospatial data, which may provide wider context and understating to support historic environment management. Table 2 identifies the main groupings of potential users who would profit from the introduction of the pilot services and outlines the potential benefits.

User Group	Example users	Benefits of pilot
Professional archaeological users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Commercial/Private archaeologists Archaeological trusts State/National archaeology services Local authority archaeology services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General data management and access Spatial planning and development control Public dissemination of information Management and publishing national historic asset inventories and archaeological events - Supports the INSPIRE (2007)⁶ and The Valletta Convention (1992)⁷ Monitoring of archaeological activities/projects Desktop based assessment exercises e.g., Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)/ Environmental Impact Statement (EIS) Identify new or at risk sites Efficient reuse of centrally acquired data and identification of areas where data already exists Exposure to cross domain datasets to enhance understanding of the wider environment
Archaeological researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Undergraduates Postgraduate Professional researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reuse and analysis of geospatial data within archaeological scholarship and research⁸ The application of spatial analysis techniques with archaeological research⁹ Enable efficient access to high quality authoritative research data Enable research to be carried out on commercially derived archaeology data Ability to publish underlying research data in its original form
Professional “non archaeological” users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning & Infrastructural development services Tourism State/National Government Local authority services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General data management and access Effective and efficient inclusion of the historic environment in state and local authority planning Mitigate the effects on the historic environment of development through informed decision making Integration of geospatial data into tourism development¹⁰ General support for growth of digital economies

⁶ INSPIRE. Data Specifications, Themes. Available online: <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/about-inspire/563> (accessed on 20 October 2022).

⁷ Council of Europe. European Convention on the Protection of the Archaeological Heritage (Revised). 1992. Available online: <https://rm.coe.int/168007bd25> (accessed on 20 October 2022).

⁸ Huggett, J. 2015. Digital Haystacks: Open Data and the Transformation of Archaeological Knowledge. In: Wilson, A and Edwards, B (eds.), Open Source Archaeology: Ethics and Practice, 6–9. Warsaw/Berlin: De Gruyter Open. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110440171-003>

⁹ Verhagen P (2012) Biting off more than we can chew? The current and future role of digital techniques in landscape archaeology. In: Kluiving SJ, Guttman-Bond E (eds) Landscape archaeology between art and science. From a multi- to an interdisciplinary approach. Amsterdam University Press, Amsterdam, pp 309–320

¹⁰ Mohammad Al-Badarneh, Abdulla Al-Shorman, Reem Alkharof & Omar Alananzeh (2022) Modelling travel time cost at petra archaeological park, Anatolia, 33:3, 426-438, DOI: 10.1080/13032917.2021.1964551

User Group	Example users	Benefits of pilot
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geospatial support in policy development and decision making
Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Archaeology interest groups • General public 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open and free access to a wider range of archaeological datasets • Support the use of citizen science programmes¹¹ • Integration of geospatial data into public engagement¹² • Provide consistent mapping for community reuse

Table 3. Groupings of potential users of the pilot services

One variable which could potentially limit the direct application of the geospatial services amongst some of the user groups would be their understanding and knowledge of how to integrate and implement the reuse of geospatial data within their own activities. For some users, direct interaction with the geospatial data will take place through developed applications, website and tools which reuse geospatial services and thus require limited technical ability.

5.4 ARIADNEplus service tested

The D4 Science gCube open-source software toolkit (<https://www.gcube-system.org/>), specifically the GeosCube which offers Spatial Data Infrastructure facilities to the research community, was tested within this pilot, while a virtual research environment (VRE) consisting of dedicated instances of a GeoServer instance and GeoNetwork instance was tested within SDI service infrastructure.

¹¹ Lambers, Karsten, Wouter B. Verschoof-van der Vaart, and Quentin P. J. Bourgeois. 2019. "Integrating Remote Sensing, Machine Learning, and Citizen Science in Dutch Archaeological Prospection" *Remote Sensing* 11, no. 7: 794. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11070794>

¹² Howland, M., Liss, B., Levy, T., & Najjar, M. (2020). Integrating Digital Datasets into Public Engagement through ArcGIS StoryMaps. *Advances in Archaeological Practice*, 8(4), 351-360. doi:10.1017/aap.2020.14

Figure 5. Illustration of the overall architecture of gCube SDI and the interaction between its components (GN:GeoNetwork, GS:GeoServer, TH:GCube Threads), after Fabio Sinibaldi¹³

GeoNetwork

GeoNetwork

open source

GeoNetwork is a geospatial directory system used to manage and catalogue geospatial referenced data through the administration of metadata. The development of GeoNetwork is one component within the larger Open-Source Geospatial Foundation ([OSGeo](https://www.osgeo.org/)) projects collections which aims to foster the global adoption of open geospatial technology through financial, organizational and legal support in the development open source geospatial solutions.

GeoNetwork platform offers several tools and functions which have been utilized within this, including:

Management of metadata records

- Use of metadata templates in the description of new geospatial resources. Standards include ISO 19115, ISO 19139, and Dublin core - only ISO 19115 was implemented in this project;
- Ability to import individual metadata records in XML or Metadata Exchange Format (MEF);

¹³ https://gcube.wiki.gcube-system.org/gcube/SDI-Service#Spatial_Data_Infrastructure_.28SDI.29_service_Overview

- Modify, edit and validate imported metadata records ensuring that the highest quality metadata is used;
- Metadata validation system which aims to improve metadata quality;
- Provide multilingual versions of metadata records to improve usability across the European region (only limited translation of non-English metadata was conducted within the pilot due to time constraints);
- Once metadata records have been imported and validated, they are published and made accessible through the public facing component of the GeoNetwork applications and available for potential users to discover and consume.

Harvesting Metadata

- Harvesting provides the ability to import remotely published metadata and store it locally within the GeoNetwork catalogue for rapid searching;
- Utilised where remote metadata is updated on a regular basis. Scheduling re-harvests within a scheduled process enables local and remote metadata to remain synchronised.

Search facilities

- Uses web interface to search for geospatial data across multiple catalogues;
- Search functionality includes
 - full-text search
 - faceted search on keywords, resource types, organizations, scale.

Map Viewer

- Enables users to interactively view and evaluate spatial data resources they have identified within the portal as relevant for their own use;
- Provides the ability to construct maps through the integrated viewing of several spatial datasets within the same environment and save these through the OGC OWS Context Conceptual Model¹⁴;
- Enabling users to reuse their constructed map views and share them with the wider research community;
- Within the ARIADNEplus pilot, the standard default GeoNetwork map was used, which employs the OpenStreetMap¹⁵ base layer for background mapping. This service was enhanced within the pilot through the integration of the Microsoft Bing Maps API service, providing aerial orthoimagery products as a base layer.

The ARIADNEplus GeoNetwork Pilot instance URL is <https://ARIADNEplus.d4science.org/geonetwork>

¹⁴Brackin, R. and Gonçalves, P. , OWS Context Conceptual Model, Open Geospatial Consortium 2014. Available online <http://www.opengeospatial.net/doc/IS/owc-conceptual/1.0>

¹⁵ <https://www.openstreetmap.org>

Figure 6: Screen capture of the ARIADNEplus GeoNetwork search interface.

GeoServer

GeoServer is a Java-based server which enables the publication of OGC compliant geospatial datasets using Web Feature Service (WFS), Web Map Service (WMS), and Web Coverage Service (WCS). It is designed with core interoperability and can handle the publication of very large datasets in both raster and vector format.

GeoServer has the ability to import data from a series of formats including:

- Vector files (.shp)
- Database (PostGIS, Oracle)
- Sever data (WFS, ArcSDE)
- Raster Data (GeoTiff, ArcGRID, ECW, ImageMosaic, JPEG2000)

Once WMS, WFS, and WCS services have been established, cartographic styling of the geospatial data is achieved through the OGC Styled Layer Descriptor (SLD) including polygon/line stroke, fill, color and thickness and simple geometric shapes for WFS and color palette, opacity, contrast for WCS.

Due to technical issues with access to the creation of a data store to import relevant test data, no WMS, WFS, or WCS have been published at the time publication of this report.

5.5 Data used for the pilot

In order to effectively test the operation of the GeoNetwork instance within the limited time of the pilot, focused efforts were scheduled in order to harvest existing data within the ARIADNEplus consortium with a focus on regions where additional metadata for the historic environment was assessable for import.

Summary of Data Harvesting/Importing into GeoNetwork Catalogue

Geospatial data sets registered within catalogue	636
Themes associated with metadata	Biota (1) Boundaries (4) Economy (1) Elevation (12) Environment (13) Imagery base maps earth cover (19) Oceans (2) Planning cadastre (3) Society (5) Transportation (1)
Formats included	CSV (3) ECW (24) ESRI Shapefile (9) File Geodatabase Feature... (5) GeoTIFF (16) GML (6) LAS (5) LAZ (4) Protected Sites Simple GML... (3) SDE Feature Class (11) Shape, WMS, WFS, GML (5) TIFF (3) WFS (9) WMS (39) WMS, WFS (6)

5.6 Description of the methodology of the test and results

The population of the GeoNetwork catalogue was therefore carried out in the following stages:

1. ARIADNEplus data

Annex 2¹⁶, through responses from the ARIADNEplus consortium and associated organisations, provided details on which geospatial services had already been published and their respective URLs. It was under the activities and research conducted in Sub-task 4.4.10, which carried out analysis of spatial data and how it can be integrated into the AO-CAT one of the outputs. Each of these datasets was harvested from the catalogue and validated in terms of active status and conformation with OGC standards: only 60% of services were valid after checking.

2. Irish and Scottish historic environment data

With the local expertise and knowledge of the Irish cultural heritage sector, relevant geospatial datasets published by Irish organisation were researched, identified and catalogued through direct harvesting of the relevant services where applicable. Where harvesting was not achieved, metadata records were sourced and imported into the catalogue system. Through the cooperation of Historic Environment Scotland's Spatial Information Manager, additional relevant metadata records were sourced for Scottish data.

3. Protected Structures INSPIRE data

Within the EU INSPIRE Directive, protected sites¹⁷ which include “protection of person-made objects including buildings, pre-historic and historic archaeological sites” would be the appropriate theme for national and regional ministries with the responsibility to publish INSPIRE compliant geospatial data. Utilising the INSPIRE Thematic Viewer (https://inspire-geoportal.ec.europa.eu/theme_selection.html?view=qsTheme) candidate datasets, which may have relevance towards the historic environment, were identified and metadata records sources were imported into the GeoNetwork Catalogue. Where specific countries displayed evidence of good quality geospatial data and associated metadata for the historic environments, an effort was made to identify additional datasets and incorporate these within the catalogue, an example of this being the Netherland's rich geospatial datasets.

5.7 VRE of the pilot

Several technical challenges and issues with data quality that reduced some of the effectiveness of the pilot came to light once the population of the GeoNetwork catalogue was terminated. These included:

- Unable to harvest services – where harvesting is tested, a “bad xml response” is returned;

¹⁶https://ariadne-infrastructure.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/T4_4_10_Final_Report_public_v1_Annex_2.xlsx

¹⁷ D2.8.I.9 Data Specification on Protected Sites Protected Sites – Technical Guidelines, 2014. Available online <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/file/1731/download?token=1pghqmA4>

- ESRI REST services – technical issues have prohibited the harvesting and integration of some ESRI REST services;
- Incomplete data – for some data publishers, the creation of full and rich metadata is sometimes missing or inconsistent in the way it is implemented. Additional issues include lack of thumbnails, which reduces the effectiveness of the catalogue when browsing the datasets;
- Occasionally, the harvesting scheduler runs into technical difficulties and requires the server instance to be restarted;
- The version of GeoNetwork on which this instance is running (3.2.1) has specific bugs which have been resolved in the most stable version (currently Ver 4.1);
- At the time of compiling this report, technical challenges to enable the transfer of files onto the server have resulted in the non-publication of additional geospatial services from the GeoServer instance.

5.8 Added value of ARIADNEPLUS for the pilot/theme and for the end user

The benefits and value created by the development of this pilot within the ARIADNEplus project include:

- The development of an integrated catalogue system for the historic environment bringing together relevant geospatial data with cultural heritage applications in one space, thus enabling a “one stop geospatial shop” approach to assisting users;
- Cataloguing the metadata across the sector enables users to observe data sourced from many institutions within a “level playing field”. It is reasonable to assume that those datasets which have richer, complete metadata records will be easier to identify and more attractive to potential users;
- The ability for users within the GeoNetwork tool to combine multiple data within a simple mapping interface that allows to save and publish the resulting map will offer limited GIS functionality for novice users, who may be put off by using standard GIS systems to construct a map;
- Once the GeoServer component becomes fully active, the shared central resources could provide the facilities to publish geospatial data for organisations that cannot afford the technical overheads of managing their own GeoServer or ESRI REST instance.

5.9 Deviation from work plan

The WCS as implemented proved to be insufficient to publish LIDAR data.

6 Task 16.4 - ARIADNEplus for sharing archaeology in 3D

6.1 Pilot description

The pilot proposed in Task 16.4 aims to demonstrate the added value of ARIADNEplus for 3D field archaeological documentation and public outreach. The task targets groups such as professional archaeologists for research purposes, archaeological and heritage institutions, and the general public for virtually experimenting with archaeology. The task builds on a rescue excavation example in Larnaca (Cyprus), where the excavation is documented in 3D. Through the service proposed in Task 15.2.3, the pilot showcases how the user can interact with the 3D model by taking measurements, including cross-sections, volumes, and plans. By recording the terrain and the entire excavation season of the site in 3D, the task proved to be a good practice example for the development of a 3D excavation diary. A metadata-based repository of the archaeological data accompanies the 3D model. Access to this platform through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure creates an innovative way of experimenting and navigating into an excavation.

6.2 Specific objectives

The pilot's objective is to demonstrate the added value of ARIADNEplus for 3D field archaeological documentation and public outreach. To do so, the pilot builds on a rescue archaeological excavation example at Hala Sultan Tekke in Larnaca (Cyprus), where the excavation of the site is 3D documented. The pilot shows how the user can interact with a 3D model of an archaeological excavation by taking measurements, including cross-sections, volumes and plans. Moreover, by recording the excavation in 3D, the pilot demonstrates a good practice example for the development of a 3D excavation diary.

6.3 Perspective users and pilot dissemination

The task identified a target audience, including professional archaeologists for various research purposes, field archaeologists for studying and managing archaeological excavations, researchers and students, archaeological and heritage institutions for management purposes, as well as the general public for outreach.

6.4 ARIADNEplus service tested

The ARIADNEplus service tested is EpHEMERA, developed by the Cyprus Institute for visualization and management of endangered heritage. EpHEMERA stands for Online 3D Database System for Endangered architectural and archaeological Heritage in the south Eastern MEediterRAnea area. On the platform it is possible to:

- Visualize, online and through standard web browsers, 3D architectural and archaeological models classified according to a specific type of risk;
- Query the database system and retrieve metadata attached to each digital object;

- Extract geometric and morphological information; moreover, the platform is open to multidisciplinary research.

Through the database architecture, the 3D models stored in a separate NAS (Network Attached Storage) server are made available online via the open-source WebGL-based PoTree viewer. PoTree is a point-based rendering solution developed explicitly for visualizing large point clouds using standard web-based technologies (Schutz 2014; Schutz & Wimmer 2015).

6.5 Data used for the pilot

The pilot uses different types of data. First of all, it uses 3D models of the excavation to be visualized and analyzed through the service platform. Secondly, images of the cultural heritage asset are used to create the access point on the platform for the viewer of the 3D model. Metadata related to the Cultural Heritage asset and the digital documentation process, including their paradata, accompany the 3D model.

6.6 Description of the methodology of the test and results

The pilot follows a specific methodology, which also coincides with the procedure for the use of the service proposed for sharing archaeology in 3D. The steps are the following:

- 3D documentation of the excavation;
- Preparation of the excavation 3D model following the requirements of the ARIADNEPLUS EpHEMERA service;
- Integration of the 3D model and its metadata description in the EpHEMERA platform;
- Analysis of the 3D model through the EpHEMERA visualizer measurement tools;
- Evaluation of the user experience (e.g., archaeologist) using the service;
- Publication of the results (e.g., scientific article).

The first step of the methodology consists of the 3D documentation of the excavation. The case study selected for the pilot relies on the excavation of the Hala Sultan Tekke site, a Late Bronze Age harbour city in Larnaca, Cyprus. The site has been excavated since the 19th century and is presently excavated by the New Swedish Cyprus expedition of the University of Gothenburg. The area currently under investigation is a cemetery composed of chamber tombs containing intact articulated inhumations, disturbed and disarticulated ones, and commingled human skeletal remains.

The recording of these complex features was difficult, so the archaeologists of the expedition decided to initiate a 3D documentation campaign of the excavation. The contexts are excavated and recorded in spits. When a feature or artefact is found, it is recorded and excavated; each time a layer is removed, the feature is documented again. This procedure continues until the area is fully excavated, at which point a final 3D data capture composed of several layers is conducted.

The successive step of the methodology consists in preparing the excavation 3D model. The 3D model obtained after applying the photogrammetric technique to the documentation of the tombs has to be adapted to the EpHEMERA service requirements. The basic requirements are, of course, the data

quality of the model (a good resolution) and that the model has to be a point cloud (texturized or not). The latter characteristic requires a specific pipeline before it is integrated into the platform. For the specific case study, since the 3D model is constituted of layers that it was vital to visualize together, each layer was imported separately to Cloud Compare. Then each layer is aligned with the previous one using the cloud-to-cloud alignment feature. Then, each layer was exported as a .las file, the extension recognized by the PoTree convertor. The layers are put through the PoTree converter 1.7, which produces the file structure compatible with the EpHEMERA platform. The file structure includes a library folder, a folder that includes the converted point cloud and an HTML file. The HTML file needs to be adjusted to reference all the point clouds' locations so they can be loaded into the platform. So, at this point, the model is ready to be uploaded to the EpHEMERA platform.

Once the 3D model has been created, the user can upload it into the Object Storage of the platform. After the 3D model has been uploaded in the Object Storage, the user can proceed to finalize the uploading of the 3D model in the EpHEMERA platform through a User Login access and using his/her credentials. At the moment, the integration of the 3D model in the EpHEMERA platform is possible through the Cyl user access. The Administrator makes sure that the model(s) are clean and in a logical size and then uploads them on the system with all the necessary metadata provided by the owner. Indeed, along with the 3D model, the user can add all the metadata information describing the Cultural Heritage asset using an associated web-form. That form is linked with the 3D model, providing a data management system for querying the database and retrieving the metadata attached to each digital object. Specifically, the structure of the metadata web-form is based on the STARC metadata, a schema developed at the Cyl that is compatible with CARARE metadata schema and CIDOC-CRM ontology. Users can also upload images of the monuments to create the profile picture of the monument in the collection using the platform design template for accessing the 3D model visualizer of the platform.

A set of metadata concerning "Standing structures" and describing the resources currently uploaded and displayed in the EpHEMERA database are under aggregation into the ARIADNE portal. Such integration creates a link between the metadata provided to ARIADNE, the digital data accessible at the provider repository/database side and the ARIADNE service to visualize and analyze them.

Finally, the 3D model and its related metadata appear on the database front-end and are accessible publicly online. The user can visualize the 3D model and interact with it through several measurement tools already integrated into the PoTree viewer and those further developed by the Cyl team and embedded in the software. In order to support the user in analyzing the 3D model, a series of documentation, tutorials and video tutorials were created within Subtask 15.2.3: a tutorial for the users' support with a list of all the available command utilities and relative descriptions to navigate, interact and perform geometric analysis of the visualized 3D archaeological assets (available online); a series of video tutorials with a visual explanation of the command utilities and functions have been created and published online on a dedicated EpHEMERA YouTube channel.

After the archaeologist analyzes the 3D model through the platform, his/her experience is evaluated through the specific questionnaire created within the WP15 task for assessing the platform. The form was further adjusted to collect feedback regarding the user's experience: from the 3D model

preparation to the final publication and its interaction within the platform. The evaluation is essential for the next and final step of the methodology.

The pilot was made possible thanks to the access provided to the EpHEMERA platform through the ARIADNE services. The first prominent accomplishment is the involvement of an external user, the distinguished University of Gothenburg archaeological mission committed to excavating an important Bronze Age site in Cyprus. The detailed explanation of the procedure, the requirements and steps needed for creating the compatible 3D model for the platform viewer allowed an archaeologist (without high technological skills) to complete the procedure. The user-friendly environment of the platform and the viewer helped archaeologists to analyze their models and advance hypotheses on the interpretation of the site.

A scientific paper on the entire procedure is being finalized for submission to a journal, while another paper proposal on the archaeological results obtained after the 3D analysis of the excavation within the platform, and the public and community engagement in archaeology has recently been submitted to a conference (MARC2023 – Mediterranean Archaeology Research Community). Other future publications on the archaeological results are also being considered.

Moreover, the pilot experience and the results will be published on Cyl's social media channels.

6.7 VRE of the pilot

The pilot results can be visualized in the EpHEMERA platform, accessible through ARIADNE's services Portal (<https://portal.ariadne-infrastructure.eu/services>) under the section "Data processing and visualization services". An EpHEMERA-Plus was created to be hosted in the ARIADNE infrastructure. A new system using an open-source stack consisting of the leading-edge Django, a high-level Python Web framework, Postgres database, Bootstrap, an open-source CSS framework, the PoTree viewer and running on virtualized Docker containers has been created (see Deliverable 15.2).

Specifically, two instances hosted in the EpHEMERA platform are dedicated to the pilot of Task 16.4 - ARIADNEplus for sharing archaeology in 3D: Tomb TT, Hala Sultan Tekke, Cyprus (<https://ephemera.cyi.ac.cy/?q=node/89>) and Tomb UU, Hala Sultan Tekke, Cyprus (<https://ephemera.cyi.ac.cy/?q=node/90>).

6.8 Added value of ARIADNEPLUS for the pilot/theme and for the end user

The integration of the EpHEMERA platform under the ARIADNE services umbrella proves the importance of ARIADNEplus for sharing archaeology in 3D.

The pilot was fundamental to allow archaeologists to visualize their archaeological excavation and the related documentation in 3D, especially in case of documentation and management of Cultural Heritage at risk (e.g., inaccessibility). The pilot for this service helped archaeologists interact with the site in a virtual environment after the excavation, which - as is well-known in the field - is a destructive and irreversible process. In particular, the feedback on the specific case study end-user underlined the following:

- The service is a valuable tool for archaeologists and specialists;
- It provides a stratigraphic visualization of deposition, strata by strata and spit by spit in a user-friendly platform;
- It is useful for the study of site formation processes, discerning intentional versus taphonomic related positioning of bones and finds, e.g., between the physical manipulation of skeletal elements compared to the movement of bones due to weather events such as storms causing water to flood into tombs and move objects, discerning the relationships between artefacts and human remains, and sequences of tomb use over time;
- It is also very valuable for the study of archaeoethanatology and funerary taphonomy, where the decompositional processes cause movement of skeletal elements through time;
- Metrically, this is an extremely valuable service and tool, particularly for overarching studies of the architectures, as it enables linear, angular and volumetric measurements of features. Particularly when dealing with tombs, which can be in unconventional shapes (e.g., bottleneck tombs), the tool provides a user-friendly way of assessing these features;
- In addition, the tool enables the rapid development of plans, maps and a holistic visualization of archaeological features;
- For bio-archaeology specialists, the tools embedded in the EpHEMERA service have an additional value with their ability to metrically measure the deposited bones virtually and after the excavation with a high level of accuracy. Such information can help to analyze the site layer by layer and enables bio-archaeologists to determine if the tomb was open or closed during the depositional period;
- Furthermore, another valuable consideration about the platform service is that it enables non-specialists, particularly those without a detailed background in digital heritage, to engage with 3D data and restudy assemblages.

In conclusion, the EpHEMERA pilot added value to ARIADNE, specifically as concerns sharing archaeology in 3D. It proved to be a useful way of experimenting and navigating into an excavation. The EpHEMERA platform service integrated into ARIADNEplus allows to access a useful service for field archaeologists and specialists, including bio-archaeologists. The service is fundamental to allow archaeologists to visualize in 3D an archaeological excavation and its related documentation, especially in case of management of Cultural Heritage at risk (e.g., inaccessibility). Last but not least, the pilot of the EpHEMERA service, through recording and analyzing the excavation in 3D, demonstrates a good practice example for developing and establishing a 3D excavation diary tool.

6.9 Deviation from the work plan

No deviations from the work planned have been experienced.

7 Task 16.5 - ARIADNEplus for public/community archaeology

7.1 Pilot description

The aim of this task is to demonstrate the added value of ARIADNEplus for non-professional archaeologists and to use ARIADNEplus as a tool to engender a sense of shared ownership in the past, thereby advancing the democratization of heritage management in Europe through the incorporation of principles of citizen science and crowd-sourcing. The task will develop, through cooperation with the metal-detecting community and other members of the public making archaeological discoveries, a strong link between professional archaeologists and the wider community. It aims at demonstrating the strong added value of the ARIADNEplus infrastructure for non-professional archaeologists. Linking professionals and community archaeology is a major issue for the project as it is a major issue for the whole profession. The task will develop the integration of metal detector finds in the ARIADNEplus infrastructure through collaboration with professional archaeologists and the newly developed Danish DIME database (user driven recording scheme for metal detector finds) and beyond, linking data across national borders from different national schemes for metal detector finds feeding data into ARIADNEplus (MEDEA, PAS, PAN, DIME, SuALT). The task will be a user-driven process with the objective of a citizen involvement in the ARIADNEplus development. The task will target groups such as community finds recording groups and individuals and non-professional heritage amateurs.

7.2 Specific objectives

The pilot aims to create a link between the professionals and community archaeology. This includes integrating the Danish metal detector finds into ARIADNEplus, testing the usability of the ARIADNEplus portal, and investigating how this usability is best communicated to the potential users. This was divided through the following points:

- Integrating DIME find data into the ARIADNEplus portal, including term mapping (which has been achieved in extension of WP 4.4.7, and an updated mapping has been made);
- Use-cases (some of which have been completed and others are in the pipeline - all of which we will attempt to 'publish' as an online exhibit and as a final report);
- Testing the usability of the ARIADNEplus portal (which has been completed, and suggestions for improvements have been implemented);
- Dissemination of the potential of the portal to the intended users, to reach the ARIADNEplus impact ambition and create awareness among the public (articles in Danish and English as are currently in progress).

With these objectives, we believe that we can reach our overall goals of highlighting the potential of ARIADNEplus as a tool for identifying, dating, and contextualizing finds for citizen scientists.

7.3 Perspective users and pilot dissemination

The expected user base includes:

- Engaged individuals (e.g., ordinary metal detectorists whom might look for comparable finds).
- Citizen scientists (e.g., metal detectorists whom wish to look beyond ‘just’ comparing finds, such as investigating distribution patterns).
- Researchers working with material culture.
- With this wide range of expected users, the task has required a multifaceted approach to how WP 16.5 is performed.
- In order to ensure that we could satisfy all these goals, a lot of time was devoted to ensuring the usability of the portal, before its use could be disseminated to the intended audiences.

7.4 ARIADNEplus service tested

We did extensive testing of the ARIADNEplus portal as a part of WP16.5. This was done to ensure that it would work as a tool for the expected users.

The testing leads back to WP4.4.7, as the manner in which data is fed into the ARIADNEplus portal also dictates what is possible - one can build a great framework, but if it is not fed the right information, it is impossible to use. Because of this, we tested both the framework and the data. A detailed description of the testing process can be seen under “Description of the methodology of the test”.

Our testing revealed some issues in both:

- Framework: It only allowed using two search parameters, if one manually defined the date range - now fixed;
- Framework: The Getty AAT hierarchy did not work, meaning that a search for a parent term (e.g., “Brooches”) did not yield its underlying types (e.g., “Ring Brooches”) - now fixed;
- Data: Some coordinates are misplaced, meaning that the heat maps are misleading;
- Data: Not all artifacts have descriptions or photographs, making them less than ideal, as it just means that one knows that finds exist, but nothing about them;
- Data: Not all collections have aligned terminology, so even though all are mapped to the Getty AAT dictionary, many use different terms. Thus, if one knows the Getty AAT term used in a given database, it is not necessarily possible to find equivalents, despite the intention of using Getty for this exact purpose. This has been fixed on our end (AU // DIME), as we have re-mapped almost 100 artifact classifications to match the ones used by other partners, to ensure the validity of cross-border searches.

Further, some decisions turned out to be less than ideal:

- Framework: Manually defined dating ranges only collected data whose entire date range was within this range. This meant that Danish items from the Middle Ages would only show up if one searched for finds from 1067-1535, but not if one searched 1068-1535. As a result, one has to actively know the date ranges of all the regions that one searches in. This has now been

changed, so that manual searches show the data of artifacts whose date range intersects with the search;

- Framework: Photographs were available on the portal for many finds, but one had to click on the object, thus leaving the search, to see these photographs. This has now been changed, so that items with available photographs are shown as thumbnails in the search results, making it much nicer to work with.

7.5 Data used for the pilot

Two main types of data have been used:

1. Artefact data, harvested from the Danish platform DIME ('public finds' / WP4.4.7). This includes descriptions, classifications, photographs, locations, dating, etc. All the data is collected in DIME and approved at the local or national museum before being harvested for ARIADNEplus. The data from DIME has been mapped to the Getty AAT terms, so that it follows a terminology that allows for cross-boundary searches in the portal. These terms were revised in October and November of 2022, in order to ensure that the selected Getty AAT terms matched the ones used by other ARIADNEplus partners and that the users have the best possible chance of locating comparable material.
2. User data. In this case, the user was post.doc. Johan Sandvang Larsen, who carried out extensive testing to see what the ARIADNEplus portal could offer to the different targeted audiences.

7.6 Description of the methodology of the test and results

The testing of the usability of the ARIADNEplus portal was carried out in multiple stages.

1. Use-testing the portal by searching a variety of artefact types using a variety of parameters and search tools. This included finds that generally cross borders in a limited period (e.g., pilgrim badges), finds that evolve for centuries but that commonly only interest users in specific periods (e.g., swords and coins), and finds that are incredibly common in metal detecting (e.g., brooches and their sub-types). This revealed some less-than-ideal aspects of the portal, which limits the usability of the desired target groups. These were communicated to Julian Richards and Pablo Millet, who were able to make changes to, and improve, the portal. This includes temporal delimitations, photographs being available as thumbnails, and malfunctioning 'parents' in the Getty AAT dictionary.
2. Testing the entire Getty AAT mapping that the DIME data was sorted under. This was done by searching every artefact classification in DIME. The search revealed almost 100 terms that would benefit from a re-mapping, to ensure a greater comparability to the Getty AAT terms used by other databases. The re-mapping has been completed at our end and uploaded to the ARIADNEplus digital structure, where it awaits the next update.
3. Use-testing the portal with all the changes that have been made, allowing for a clearer picture of the great potential that the portal holds. This use-test is designed to show the many different aspects of the portal that the intended users are likely to utilize, i.e., finding comparable materials across borders and/or investigating distribution patterns.

4. Disseminating the potential of the portal and the ARIADNEplus vision of cross-border collaboration to the intended users. This will be achieved through a small online exhibit and two articles in popular journals.

7.7 VRE of the pilot

The pilot was not linked to a specifically designed VRE, since the objective was to make finds data directly available to all (scientists, citizen scientists and members of the public). All requirements for using data for research are fulfilled by the standard set up of the ARIADNEplus portal.

7.8 Added value of ARIADNEPLUS for the pilot/theme and for the end user

ARIADNEplus has allowed for this potential to be revealed – an international over-arching database allowing cross-border comparisons of artefacts is a dream come true. While there is still much that can be done to improve the data that is fed into the ARIADNEplus database (e.g., available photographs, descriptions, etc.), it can be used as a tool to make the target audience familiar with an international perspective, ensuring that they are more prone to using a database similar to ARIADNEplus in the future. The recent addition of the Finnish dataset shows that ARIADNEplus is still growing and continues to be relevant.

7.9 Deviation from the work plan

One of the main activities was the preparation of the portal for the intended groups, to ensure that the users' first experience with the portal would be a positive one. This required a vast amount of testing. At present, a substantial effort is dedicated to dissemination initiatives, among others a small online exhibition and two articles in popular journals.

8 Task 16.6 - ARIADNEplus for understanding ancient and present cities: scanning the heart of Rome

8.1 Pilot description

The task proposes a well-defined area in Rome, roughly corresponding to the Esquiline Hill, which comprises the modern districts of Monti and Esquilino, densely urbanized after 1871, when Rome became the Capital of the Italian Kingdom.

The case study area in the contemporary city

Archaeological map of the case study area

In ancient times, the Esquiline was a boundary zone between the urban and extra-urban areas, that now provides archaeological data about both funerary and settlement contexts. A wide necropolis developed along the viae Labicana and Tiburtina since the 8th century BC until the first imperial period. Monumental buildings, such as the Porticus Liviae, the Macellum Liviae, the Porticus Esquilinus, but also private urban villas as the Horti Maecenatis and the Horti Lamiani, were built during the first imperial period and used until the late antiquity.

The finds from the Esquiline excavations (grave goods from the necropolis, statues, frescoes from the Horti etc.) are collected in numerous museum collections and described in many archive documents, scientific papers and books.

8.2 Specific objectives

The main goal of Task 16.6 is to map the transformations of a multi-layered urban area, with successive life phases in the same areas from ancient times to the present day through archaeological and archival sources (archaeological findings in museum collections, scientific publications, historical cartography, etc.).

In multi-stratified urban areas, archaeological investigation and more generally the reconstruction of the diachronic development of the city can take advantage of many different sources of information, but at the same time it is complicated to systematize and standardize them to use them within a single database. The other specific objective of the Pilot has been to use the data collected from different sources, mapping them to the Italian national standard. The city center of Rome contains some of the most complex urban stratigraphy in Europe and requires specific strategies for managing its

archaeological heritage, constantly threatened by the expansion of the contemporary city. Therefore, the Sitar Project, the open archaeological database of Rome, represented the ideal partner for the experimentation of Task 16.6. The other important challenge featured the Database mapping of a particularly complex and articulated data structure to make it interoperable with the National Geoportal for Archaeology – GNA - that the Central Institute for Archaeology (ICA) has developed over the last years, also thanks to the participation in the ARIADNEplus Project, in order to connect all existing databases through a single national access point.

8.3 Perspective users and pilot dissemination

The task mainly addresses State and professional archaeologists, other public bodies (municipality, government...) and experts (e.g., architects, geologists) involved in urban planning and transformation, which must take into account the multiple transformations of an area not only in the ancient age, but also and above all in the modern age. The anthropic activity of the last 200 years has in fact dramatically altered the urban subsoil and consequently the archaeological deposits preserved in it. The task is also of interest to academic researchers.

8.4 ARIADNEplus service tested

The GeoPortal Framework designed by the CNR-ISTI of Pisa is the ARIADNEplus service selected to develop the Pilot. The GeoPortal Framework is a feature-complete framework enabling the publication, access and management of GIS projects consisting of multiple payloads (such as documents, images, and datasets), each described with tailored metadata.

There was no need to create a new service; the one already developed in WP 15 was re-used for this Pilot.

Figure 7. General Architecture of the Geoportal Framework

8.5 Data used for the pilot

Archaeological data used for the pilot come from the open archaeological database SITAR Archaeological Information System of Rome (Sistema Informativo Territoriale Archeologico di Roma): 349 interventions (excavations, surveys, etc.) were catalogued, for a total of 1150 archaeological structures, distinguished by chronology and function; SITAR database is an Open access portal developed by the superintendency of Rome since 2010, and it contains information about the territory of the municipality of Rome. Many of the archaeological findings archived in the SITAR DB are only known from ancient cartography (especially XIX century urban plans), ancient photos and drawings (especially from XIX century).

8.6 Description of the methodology of the test and results

There are several archaeological portals in Italy that systematize and publish archaeological data online, but they all follow different standards and data-models. The Central Institute for Archaeology, with the National Geoportal for Archaeology, has developed a minimum standard, based on the Italian standard for cultural heritage catalogue (ICCD), to connect already existing databases. To put it briefly, the mapping of data between the two models starts from the distinction between the type of intervention (e.g., an excavation, survey, study, etc. – called Origin of information in SITAR and MOPR, i.e., project form, in GNA) and the investigated archaeological data (called archaeological part in SITAR and MOSI, i.e., site form, in GNA). These two levels, which have been mapped field by field on the GNA data model, correspond to the distinction between event and record used by the ARIADNE Portal.

Figure 8. The standards developed by ICCD

8.7 VRE of the pilot

The Virtual Research Environment used in this phase, provided by CNR ISTI, is currently private. It will become openly accessible after validation of the data performed by WP16 data experts.

Link: <https://ariadne.d4science.org/web/esquiline>

ESQUILINE AREA

The Esquiline was a boundary zone between the urban and extra-urban areas, providing archaeological data about both funerary and settlement contexts.

Along the viae Labicana and Tiburtina a wide necropolis developed since the 8th century BC until the first imperial period. Monumental buildings as the Porticus Liviae, the Macellum Liviae, the Porticus Esquilinus, but also private urban villas as the horti Maecenatis and the horti Lamiani were built in first imperial period and used until the Late antiquity

The finds from the Esquiline excavations (graves goods from the necropolis, statues, frescoes from the Horti etc.) are collected in the National Roman Museum, in the Capitoline Museums and in the Centrale Montemartini Museum. Different GIS layers collect, integrate and display data coming from 19th century excavations and historical cartography in a spatio-temporal database, allowing the reconstruction of the transformation of an urban landscape through the centuries.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the Esquiline page

8.8 Added value of ARIADNEplus for the pilot/theme and for the end user

The added value represented by the services and the partnership within the ARIADNEplus project is represented above all by the possibility of comparing experiences and methodologies that attempt to solve complex problems common to all large multi-layered urban realities. Moreover, at the national level, the ARIADNEplus Project represented a strong push towards the structuring of a national standard for the online registration and publication of data derived from archaeological research carried out on the Italian territory. In fact, up to now the existing projects were not based on the same standard, especially as regards preventive archaeology and, more generally, the protection activity.

8.9 Deviation from the work plan

No deviations from the work plan have been experienced.

9 Task 16.7 - Exploiting the ARIADNEplus Data Infrastructure to understand complex phenomena of the Past

9.1 Pilot description

The task highlights the added-value of ARIADNEplus for academic projects addressing the Grand Challenges in archaeological research. It builds on the connection between the largest dataset of amphorae inscriptions and ARIADNEplus. The database created by CEIPAC in 1995 represents the largest available dataset of amphorae epigraphy, its relational repository with more than 43,000 entries of both amphorae stamps and tituli picti.

A specific ontology has been developed within the EPnet project to integrate the dataset with the Heidelberg Datenbank and the Pleiades geographical dataset by relying on the OBDI paradigm, to create a more functional database to historical and archaeological research. The database is a major tool for exploring different hypotheses and theories about Roman economy and Mediterranean trade routes.

The pilot aims to explore how the integration of such data within ARIADNEplus may provide new insights into Roman trade routes and the links created by the olive oil trade between Baetica and Rome, as resulting from the inscriptions on amphorae used for transporting the oil to Rome, which were disposed of after delivery and created the famous mount Testaccio in Rome.

9.2 Specific objectives

The specific objectives of the pilot were to build on the connection between the largest dataset of amphorae epigraphy and ARIADNEplus by testing integration and cross search, taking into account the ontology previously developed by CEIPAC.

9.3 Perspective users and pilot dissemination

Main targeted audiences are:

- Archaeologists specialized in Roman period;
- Epigraphists;
- High level students;
- Museums;
- Specialized amateurs

The pilot results were disseminated through specialized conferences of the sector such as CAA, EAA, Limescongress Nijmegen 2022 and through scientific papers¹⁸.

9.4 ARIADNEplus service tested

The pilot tested the possibilities of cross-searching the infrastructure's portal following data integration and using the internet search engine developed by ARIADNEplus.

9.5 Data used for the pilot

- The aggregation of over 57000 inscriptions and one million of data, all in all;
- The pilot used the database created by EPnet to map the semantic structure to the ARIADNEplus ontology and epigraphy application profile (Subtask 4.4.13);
- Some key words, such as amphora, epigraphy, stamp or Dressel 20 were tested, and the search was compared in both the CEIPAC database and in ARIADNEplus.

9.6 Description of the methodology of the test and results

- Search the keywords;
- Compile and analyse results;
- Compare results in order to highlight the added-value of ARIADNEplus data aggregation.

Through the development of this pilot, the project was able to integrate the ontology of the CEIPAC database within ARIADNEplus. The data returned by the infrastructure are more numerous than the that returned by CEIPAC alone, as ARIADNE also contains data aggregated from other connected databases. The possibilities for the development of new studies about amphorae epigraphy, precisely, are enormous. The open access data give also a plus of interconnectivity further than the options that the previous database offered.

9.7 VRE of the pilot

No specific VRE was developed for the task.

¹⁸ Remesal Rodríguez, J., & Pérez González, J. (Eds.). (2022). *Arqueología y Técnica: Métodos formales, nuevos enfoques: Archaeology and Techne: Formal methods, new approaches*. Archaeopress. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv2b07v2z>

Bermúdez Lorenzo, J. M. (2021). From CIL XV to the CEIPAC Database: Some Results of Dissemination Data. In I. V. Soriano & D. E. Espinosa (Eds.), *Epigraphy in the Digital Age: Opportunities and Challenges in the Recording, Analysis and Dissemination of Inscriptions* (pp. 185–192). Archaeopress. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1xsm8s5.21>

9.8 Added value of ARIADNEplus for the pilot/theme and for the end user

The aggregation of the data provided by the ARIADNEplus infrastructure allows to establish searches and obtain results that are not only related to the CEIPAC database, but also to the other databases connected to the project. These can be used to explore new, broader approaches of research and this can be interesting for historians and archaeologists.

9.9 Deviation from the work plan

Considering the interdependence from other tasks, notably 4.4.13, it was expected that this pilot would start late in the project. The development was affected by changes in the team at UB which took some time to complete and caused a stop in the pilot development. After this initial delay, the pilot had no deviation from the work plan.

10 Task 16.8: ARIADNEplus for preventive archaeology

10.1 Pilot description

The task highlights the value of ARIADNEplus for preventive archaeology (also variously known as rescue, developer-funded, or contract archaeology in some countries, according to their legislative systems). What they have in common is that an unfortunate split has often developed between the state organizations, museums or commercial contractors who undertake most excavation and fieldwork (generating primary research data) and the archaeologists working in research institutes and universities (who consume the data and also generate synthesis and interpretation). This has created a dangerous gap, whereby archaeological synthesis may be years out-of-date, and new fieldwork may be undertaken without any research context. The task will demonstrate the value of ARIADNEplus in bridging that gap.

The pilot deploys the ARIADNEplus NLP¹⁹ services to extract added value (indexing, tagging, harmonization of terminologies etc.) from the vast quantity of grey literature (unpublished fieldwork reports) made available Open Access by the INRAP (with additional potential cases studies in Dutch, English and Italian), making the data more accessible for researchers. In return, it demonstrates to those undertaking fieldwork that ARIADNEplus can enhance their public and research profile and make their primary data re-usable, thereby encouraging them to provide greater access and showing the value and impact of the application of the FAIR principles to preventive archaeology.

The ARIADNE project had previously conducted several experiments to apply NLP to archaeological reports, using both rule-based and machine learning approaches combined with domain vocabularies and thesauri²⁰.

Named entity recognition (NER) models were generated with the GATE²¹ Toolkit in English, Dutch, and Swedish by the University of South Wales, with the collaboration of the Leiden University & the Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS) for Dutch reports, and the Swedish National Data Service (SND) for Swedish reports. Two types of NER models were created for each language: one targeted to detect general concepts found in the reports (archaeological context, material, physical object, monument, place, and time appellation) and one dedicated to a case study on dendrochronology. One additional model was designed in English on a numismatic case study. All seven pipelines are open-source and available on GitHub²².

¹⁹ NLP (Natural Language Processing) combines linguistics, computer science, mathematics, and artificial intelligence to model and reproduce, with the help of machines, the human capacity to produce and understand linguistic statements. See and Cori, M., & Léon, J. (2002). La constitution du TAL. *Revue TAL*, 43(3), p. 22.

²⁰ Vlachidis, A., Tudhope, D., Wansleben, M., Azzopardi, J., Green, K., Xia, L. & Wright, H. (2017). *D16.4: Final Report on Natural Language Processing*. Technical report, ARIADNE.

²¹ General architecture for text engineering, <https://gate.ac.uk/> (consulted 27.10.2022).

²² <https://github.com/avlachid/Multilingual-NLP-for-Archaeological-Reports-Ariadne-Infrastructure> (consulted 27.10.2022).

Furthermore, the Archaeology Data Service at the University of York developed an API with the help of machine learning to automatically extract named entities to generate metadata.

Regarding ARIADNEplus, readers are also invited to refer back to Deliverable 15.2 for information related to Task 15.4, dedicated to implementing the text mining and NLP services.

10.2 Specific objectives

The pilot specifically aimed to try out the INCEpTION web application – one of the services hosted on the ARIADNEplus platform – and test the benefit in terms of cost and practicality of using machine learning techniques on archaeological reports. INCEpTION²³ is an open-source text-annotation platform developed by the Ubiquitous Knowledge Processing (UKP) Lab of the *Technische Universität Darmstadt*; such tools are used in supervised machine learning to create the human-annotated data required to train and test models. INCEpTION has been implemented on the ARIADNEplus D4Science portal, in the ARIADNEplus LAB Virtual Research Environment²⁴.

10.3 Perspective users and pilot dissemination

NLP techniques are particularly relevant when dealing with a large volume of data, too large to be treated and analysed by humans. This phenomenon – known as big data – is also found in archaeology, where the digitalization and development of open access of the discipline in the last twenty years have led to the creation and diffusion of data (datasets, reports, etc.) in unprecedented volumes. Facing this ‘data deluge’²⁵, NLP can be used to exploit large corpora, for example by automatically indexing them or by providing more efficient ways to query their content, going beyond metadata and full-text search. This pilot – and more broadly NLP applied to archaeology – is thus aimed primarily at structures holding large amounts of archaeological data (rescue archaeology operators, heritage institutions, archives, etc.) and consequently, their users (professional "contract" archaeologists, researchers, students, amateurs, etc.), fostering the exchange of knowledge between the two. ARIADNEplus users may also be encouraged to create their own models to better understand their data.

10.4 ARIADNEplus service tested

INCEpTION NLP service and more specifically its web application was tested.

²³ Klie, J.-C., Bugert, M., Boullosa, B., Eckart de Castilho, R. & Gurevych, I. (2018). The INCEpTION Platform: Machine-Assisted and Knowledge-Oriented Interactive Annotation. In *Proceedings of System Demonstrations of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics (COLING 2018)*, Santa Fe, New Mexico, USA. INCEpTION can also be directly downloaded from its website <https://inception-project.github.io/> (consulted 27.10.2022). See also <https://github.com/inception-project/inception> (consulted 27.10.2022).

²⁴ https://ariadne.d4science.org/group/ARIADNEplus_lab/inception (consulted 27.10.2022).

²⁵ Bevan, A. (2015). The data deluge. *Antiquity*, 89(348), pp. 1473–1484.

10.5 Data used for pilot

The data used for the pilot consisted of six French field reports provided by INRAP: five survey reports and one excavation report, for a total volume of *circa* 500 pages (or 133,414 tokens²⁶). The files were retrieved in PDF format from *Dolia*, INRAP's information system for documentary resources²⁷.

10.6 Description of the methodology of the test and results

The first step of the process was the extraction of the raw text from our PDF files. After testing several tools (pdfminer.six²⁸, PyPDF2²⁹, PyMuPDF³⁰, and textract³¹), pdftotext of the Poppler library³² proved to be more efficient, both in terms of speed and accuracy.

Following the extraction, we performed sentence segmentation on the files to try to rebuild and identify the sentences of the reports to facilitate the annotation task and improve the training of the models. The data was afterwards tokenized. The sentence segmentation and tokenization of the corpus were conducted with the help of the spaCy open-source library³³ and its French model "fr_core_news_lg". Although not perfect –mainly because of the complexity of the layout of the reports³⁴ – the resulting data was sound enough to be used for annotation.

The reports were then imported into INCEption to be annotated by a group of four members from INRAP (Figure 10). Being inexperienced with INCEption and NLP in general, we appreciated the extensive documentation³⁵ and tutorials³⁶ created by the UKP Lab, as well as their availability and willingness to answer users' questions³⁷.

Six types of entities were annotated³⁸ :

- **CHRONO**, for temporal references ("Antiquity", "XIIth century", "200 BC", etc.).
- **CONTEXTE**, for archaeological features ("pit", "ditch", "wall", "hearth", etc.).

²⁶ "A token is an instance of a sequence of characters in some particular document that are grouped together as a useful semantic unit for processing". See Manning, C. D., Raghavan, P., & Schütze, H. (2008). *Introduction to Information Retrieval*. Cambridge University Press, p. 22. Tokens often consist of the units making up a sentence (words, numbers, punctuation marks, etc.).

²⁷ <https://dolia.inrap.fr/> (consulted 27.10.2022).

²⁸ <https://github.com/pdfminer/pdfminer.six> (consulted 29.10.2022).

²⁹ <https://github.com/py-pdf/PyPDF2> (consulted 29.10.2022).

³⁰ <https://github.com/pymupdf/PyMuPDF> (consulted 29.10.2022).

³¹ <https://github.com/deanmalmgren/textract> (consulted 29.10.2022).

³² <https://gitlab.freedesktop.org/poppler/poppler> (consulted 27.10.2022).

³³ <https://spacy.io/>; see also <https://github.com/explosion/spaCy> (consulted 27.10.2022).

³⁴ Titles of sections, mentions of figures or tables and inventories caused for instance some difficulties. Sentences were sometimes also cut for no reason (between "Middle" and "Ages" every so often for example), presumably due to faulty training data.

³⁵ <https://inception-project.github.io/documentation/> (consulted 20.11.2022).

³⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL5Hz5pttaJ96SIXHGRZf8KziYvpVHioL-> (consulted 20.11.2022).

³⁷ Questions can be directly asked on the project's [GitHub repository](#), as well as on a [Google Group](#) (consulted 20.11.2022).

³⁸ The following examples were translated from French.

- **INTERVALLE**, for time spans ("from the Neolithic to the late Antiquity", "VIIth-IXth centuries", "between 50 and 70 AD", etc.).
- **MAT**, for materials ("bronze", "dolerite", "ceramic", etc.).
- **MOB**, for physical finds ("bones", "pottery shards", "roof tile", etc.).
- **TECH_STYLE**, for mentions of techniques and styles of fabrication or construction ("carved", "glazed", "polished", etc.).

An additional entity for mentions of animal and plant species was subsequently deleted from the corpus due to an insufficient number of examples.

The screenshot shows the INCEpTION web interface. The main area displays a document with several lines of text. Various words and phrases are highlighted with colored boxes: green for 'Contexte' (CONTEXT) and yellow for 'Chronology' (CHRONO). For example, 'haut Moyen Âge' is highlighted in yellow, and 'ornières' is highlighted in green. The right sidebar shows the 'Annotation' panel, which is currently displaying a 'Named entity' layer. The text 'haut Moyen Âge' is shown, along with its identifier 'haut Moyen Âge'. Below this, there is a description: 'Période historique qui commence en 476 par la chute du dernier empereur romain d'Occident, et s'achève en l'an 1000.' The value 'CHRONO' is also visible. The bottom of the interface shows the footer: 'Technische Universität Darmstadt – Computer Science Department – INCEpTION – 23.8 (2022-06-29 21:24:41, build 4b271961)'.

Figure 10: Annotating a document with INCEpTION

Even if the main focus was to eventually train a named entity recognition model, we enriched our annotation with two other tasks to deepen our use of INCEpTION. The Pactols knowledge base³⁹ – created by the *Fédération et Ressources sur l'Antiquité*⁴⁰ (Frantiq) and developed with the support of the MASA consortium⁴¹ - "*Mémoire des archéologues et des sites archéologiques*" – was therefore imported into INCEpTION to link its entries to our annotated entities (except INTERVALLE entities), thus creating a corpus that could be used in the future to train an entity linking model. Relations were also created between the entities to allow the data to be used to train a relation extraction model. The long and tedious annotation process was facilitated by INCEpTION's human-in-the-loop system⁴²,

³⁹ Note: as of late September 2022, Pactols has evolved into a newer version, aligned with the Backbone Thesaurus. The annotated data is up-to-date with the new version. See <https://pactols.frantiq.fr/opentheso/> (consulted 27.10.2022).

⁴⁰ <https://www.frantiq.fr> (consulted 28.11.2022).

⁴¹ <https://masa.hypotheses.org/> (consulted 28.11.2022).

⁴² Klie, J.-C., Eckart de Castilho, R. and Gurevych, I. (2020). From Zero to Hero: Human-In-The-Loop Entity Linking in Low Resource Domains. *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, pp. 6982–6993.

where machine-learning-powered recommenders learn from the annotators' practices to suggest annotations, thus reducing the human effort.

After the curation of our data, where all the annotations made by the team were compared and selected, the final corpus contains 5078 entities (1082 CHRONO, 2399 CONTEXTE, 225 INTERVALLE, 123 MAT, 1170 MOB and 79 TECH_STYLE). It is available on an online repository⁴³.

Figure 11: Method used for training and testing the NER models

The annotated corpus was afterwards exported in CoNLL 2002 format and used to train a NER transformer-based model with spaCy. A single report with a volume roughly equivalent to ten percent of the annotated data was held out as a test set, while the remaining documents were used as a "learning" set. To have a better idea of the quality of the models created with the annotated data, we decided to do a 5-fold cross-validation⁴⁴ on the learning set. The learning set was therefore shuffled and divided into five blocks of equal size and assembled into five folds. For each fold, one rotating block was used as the development set (also named validation set), while the remaining four were used as the training set. The five models thus generated were then evaluated against the same test set previously mentioned (Figure 11).

The models were evaluated according to the classical NLP metrics of recall, precision, and F1 score. Recall evaluates the ability of a model to detect the presence of entities (e.g., the model has identified "amphora" as a named entity), while precision assesses the ability of a model to assign the correct label to an entity (e.g., the model has assigned the label MOB to "amphora"). The F1 score is the harmonic means of recall and precision and as such, it gives a general evaluation measure for a model. The closer the metrics are to a hundred, the better the score.

⁴³ https://github.com/InrapFr/NLP_for_French_Archaeological_Reports_ARIADNEplus.

⁴⁴ Moss, H. B., Leslie, D. S., & Rayson, P. (2018). Using J-K fold Cross Validation to Reduce Variance When Tuning NLP Models. *ArXiv:1806.07139*. Jurafsky, D., & Martin, J. H. (2022). *Speech and Language Processing. An introduction to Natural Language Computational Linguistics, and Speech Recognition* (Third Edition draft), p.70.

Once evaluated on the test set, our models obtained an average F1 score of 79, with a recall of 78 and a precision of 80⁴⁵. Though encouraging, given the low volume of the annotated corpus, the average F1 scores for each type of entity can vary drastically. If the CHRONO, CONTEXTE, INTERVALLE, and MOB entities all got satisfying numbers (86, 82, 86, 73 respectively), TECH_STYLE fell at 41 and MAT at 12. These numbers can be explained by a lack of training data compared to the other entities⁴⁶; they also demonstrate the ambiguity surrounding certain concepts. Materials are for instance notably difficult to annotate and train a model on due to their often-equivocal nature in archaeological reports. "Pottery" for example can both be a physical find or a material depending on the sentence, and information about the materials composing the natural ground – which we didn't annotate – is also frequently found in the reports. This confusion was noted in the annotation and training processes alike⁴⁷. The human factor is indeed not to be overlooked, as the long and repetitive task of annotation can lead to discrepancies or misses among entities, despite the use of annotation guidelines and proofreading.

An example of predictions made by a model trained with the annotated data can be found below (Figure 12).

Un **racloir MOB** du **Paléolithique moyen CHRONO** a été retrouvé au fond de la **fosse CONTEXTE** 7, tandis que le **silo CONTEXTE** a livré les fragments d'un **pot MOB** en **céramique MAT** datant de **La Tène D CHRONO** (**150 à 30 avant notre ère INTERVALLE**). Deux bords de **cruches MOB** **médiévales CHRONO** **peintes TECH_STYLE** (**Moyen Âge classique CHRONO** , **XIIe siècle CHRONO**) sont également à signaler.

A **scraper** from the **Middle Palaeolithic** was found at the bottom of **pit** 7, while the **sil** yielded the fragments of a **ceramic pot** dating from **La Tène D (150 to 30 BC)**. Two rims of **medieval painted jugs (High Middle Ages, 12th century)** were also found.

Figure 12: Predictions made on a made-up example by a model trained with the annotated data

Created as a test of the INCEpTION annotation platform, this corpus was able to train models with encouraging results. As errors still occur frequently, it remains, however, at an experimental level and would need larger volumes of data to be properly implemented. As we found out with this task, the creation of such a corpus would require important time and human resources, weeks or months of the contribution of experts in the field in order to produce quality data (which would not prevent human mistakes). It should also be noted that working on structured files would greatly improve the annotation and training processes⁴⁸ and would enable the creation of a pipeline allowing for the resulting identified entities to be properly encoded within the text, thus automatically enriching the reports.

⁴⁵ Similar results were obtained without cross-validation using as the development set a single report of a volume roughly equal to ten percent of the annotated data (different from the one used as the test set).

⁴⁶ A stratified cross-validation would help dealing with the uneven occurrences of entity types.

⁴⁷ The specific issue regarding entities related to materials is often found in archeological-related NLP projects. See for example the aforementioned ARIADNE final report on NLP (Vlachidis *et al.*, 2017, p. 12) or Brandsen, A. (2022). *Digging in documents: Using text mining to access the hidden knowledge in Dutch archaeological excavation reports* [PhD Thesis, Leiden University], p. 44.

⁴⁸ As well as remove the sometimes problematic text extraction step.

Within Task 16.8 of ARIADNEplus, an experiment⁴⁹ was conducted by Ceri Binding and Douglas Tudhope from the Hypermedia Research Group of the University of South Wales in order to apply rule-based techniques to detect temporal entities in the abstracts of 481 archaeological reports provided by the INRAP. The reports were provided in PDF format, with an additional XML file containing UNIMARC-formatted metadata related to the documents. After the text extraction of the PDF files, the spaCy open-source library was used to tokenize the data and apply hand-crafted rules to extract the named entities. If the patterns initially took into account spaCy's part of speech tagging, it was later on abandoned due to mistakes with the resulting tags.

The first version of the experiment aimed to identify the following temporal entities⁵⁰:

- **Date prefixes** ("beginning of", "end of", "during the", "second half of", etc.).
- **Dates suffixes** ("BC", "AD", "BP", "cal BC", etc.).
- **Centuries / millennia** ("first century", "3rd century", "5th millennium", etc.).
- **Century spans** ("4th and 5th century", "3rd and 4th century", etc.).
- **Year spans** ("2013 to 2016", etc.).
- **Years** ("1920s", "year 2007", "in 1765", etc.).
- **Named periods** ("Medieval", "Bronze age", "Roman era", etc.).

The patterns were written in JSON as sequential arrays and used regular expressions. An example and its explanation by C. Binding and D. Tudhope can be found below:

```
{
  "label": "CENTURYSPAN",
  "pattern": [
    { "LOWER": "century", "REGEX": "(er?|[eè]me)$" },
    { "OP": "?", "LOWER": { "REGEX": "^s(\\.|iècle)?$" },
    { "LOWER": { "REGEX": "(au|[-])$" },
    { "LOWER": "century", "REGEX": "(er?|[eè]me)$" },
    { "OP": "?", "LOWER": { "REGEX": "^s(\\.|iècles)?$" }
  ]
}
```

This pattern will match a span of centuries. The pattern locates ordinals expressed either as Roman numerals (e.g., "XVIII" - 18th) or as numbers ("5^{ème}" - 5th) optionally accompanied by the word "siècle" or its abbreviation "s." (century), separated by either a hyphen or by the

⁴⁹ The full reports on the experimentation can be found below as an appendix.

⁵⁰ The following examples were translated from French.

word "au" (to) – incorporating regular expressions in this manner allows the pattern to cater for a number of different variants, e.g., "*VIe-IXe siècles*" (6th-9th centuries), or "*Xe siècle au XIe siècle*" (9th century to 11th century). The pattern enforces lowercase text comparisons for case insensitive matching.

In addition to the empirical identification of year spans and numbered centuries, an INRAP Perio.do collection⁵¹, metadata from the INRAP files implemented on ARIADNEplus, and a spreadsheet list provided by the INRAP were used to match named periods. The patterns were subsequently modified in the light of the initial results to take better account of abbreviations, diacritics and variations in punctuation or spelling.

A second version of the experiment used a Perio.do collection⁵² for named periods, allowing for easy updates and utilization by the NER output of the date ranges associated with each entry. The dates prefixes and suffixes were also incorporated to century or year spans, allowing "the possibility in future work of refining associated numerical date range with agreed estimates for 'early', 'late' etc. for say century sub-divisions".

The experiment seems to work well for temporal expressions, while lone year values are not consistently identified correctly. An example of the results can be found below⁵³, compared with the temporal predictions made on the same text by a model trained with our INCEpTION-annotated data (Figure 13). Both approaches have globally successfully detected and identified temporal entities. If the machine learning approach appears to have here richer results ("*Bronze final IIIb*" instead of "*Bronze final*", "*premier tiers du Ier s. av. n. ère*" instead of "*Ier s. av. n. ère*"), the correctness of the entities recognized and their tagging can greatly vary from one model to another, while a rule-based approach guarantees consistency in the results.

⁵¹ <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0rrjd9> (consulted 28.11.2022).

⁵² <http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4> (consulted 28.11.2022).

⁵³ The results were obtained with the first version of the rule-based experiment.

au Bas-Empire PERIOD , ont été relevées sur le site. La période la mieux documentée étant le deuxième âge du Fer PERIOD , période qui fait l'objet de très nombreuses découvertes dans le quartier de la plaine Saint-Roch, depuis plus d'un siècle. Les traces d'occupations les plus anciennes sont datées du Bronze final IIIb où une aire d'habitat semble s'être développée sur ce secteur, et s'inscrivent dans un recouvrement limoneux, dans lequel des artefacts datant du Chalcolithique PERIOD ont été recueillis. La période qui succède à ces premiers niveaux d'occupations est la fin du DATEPREFIX second âge du Fer PERIOD , rompant ainsi un hiatus chronologique s'échelonnant du VIIIe s. CENTURYSpan au milieu du DATEPREFIX IIe s. CENTURYSpan av. notre ère DATESUFFIX . Le début de DATEPREFIX cette occupation gauloise a été daté du milieu du DATEPREFIX IIe s. CENTURYSpan pour perdurer sans interruption jusqu'au premier tiers du Ier s. CENTURYSpan av. n. ère DATESUFFIX . Trois phases caractérisées par des réaménagements du site ont été distinguées. Les deux premières semblent regrouper des activités domestiques assez similaires au sein d'un îlot « d'habitats » délimité par un fossé. Les puits font leur apparition à la transition entre le IIe et le Ier s. CENTURYSpan av. n. ère DATESUFFIX . Un vaste épandage de morceaux d'amphores mêlé à des galets, constituant ainsi un niveau de circulation, caractérise la fin des occupations gauloises sur le site et semble répondre à de nouveaux besoins. Ce type d'aménagement, comme l'interruption de l'occupation constatée pour une grande partie du Ier s. CENTURYSpan av. n. ère DATESUFFIX .

au Bas-Empire CHRONO , ont été relevées sur le site. La période la mieux documentée étant le deuxième âge du Fer CHRONO , période qui fait l'objet de très nombreuses découvertes dans le quartier de la plaine Saint-Roch, depuis plus d'un siècle. Les traces d'occupation les plus anciennes sont datées du Bronze final IIIb CHRONO , où une aire d'habitat semble s'être développée sur ce secteur, et s'inscrivent dans un recouvrement limoneux, dans lequel des artefacts datant du Chalcolithique CHRONO ont été recueillis. La période qui succède à ces premiers niveaux d'occupations est la fin du second âge du Fer CHRONO , rompant ainsi un hiatus chronologique s'échelonnant du VIIIe s. au milieu du IIe s. av. notre ère INTERVALLE . Le début de cette occupation gauloise CHRONO a été daté du milieu du IIe s. CHRONO pour perdurer sans interruption jusqu'au premier tiers du Ier s. av. n. ère CHRONO . Trois phases caractérisées par des réaménagements du site ont été distinguées. Les deux premières semblent regrouper des activités domestiques assez similaires au sein d'un îlot "d'habitats" délimité par un fossé. Les puits font leur apparition à la transition entre le IIe et le Ier s. av. n. ère INTERVALLE . Un vaste épandage de morceaux d'amphores mêlé à des galets, constituant ainsi un niveau de circulation, caractérise la fin des occupations gauloises CHRONO sur le site et semble répondre à de nouveaux besoins. Ce type d'aménagements, comme l'interruption de l'occupation constatée pour une grande partie du Ier s. av. n. ère CHRONO .

Figure 13: Example of temporal entities recognized with rule-based (top) and machine learning (bottom) approaches

If rule-based approaches need linguistic and computer science knowledge in order to create the matching patterns, they have the advantage of not requiring the time-consuming annotation of a large volume of data. However, they might be less efficient and adaptable on unstructured or fuzzy data, since the rules only catch the precise matching pattern associated. Though temporal entities can generally be limited to a certain vocabulary and patterns, physical finds or archaeological features

might be more elusive given their greater versatility, thus illustrating the added-value of INCEpTION and annotated corpora.

10.7 Added value of ARIADNEplus for the pilot and end-user

Through its implementation of INCEpTION on its D4Science portal, ARIADNEplus promotes and encourages the use of natural language processing to the archaeological community, thus inciting the development of tools to better understand, manage and exploit archaeological data at the time of the ‘data deluge’. INCEpTION proved to be a powerful and well-documented tool, more practical than other free text-annotation platforms that we tested. We do regret however the absence of JSONL format and the occasional slowness of the tool. Also, PDF annotation, although normally supported by INCEpTION, could not unfortunately be tested due to bugs.

If the platform can seem daunting at first for NLP novices, its variety of input⁵⁴ and output⁵⁵ formats and available tasks for textual resources (named entity tagging, part-of-speech tagging, relation creation, links to knowledge bases, and so on), coupled with a machine-learning-powered help for annotation, puts INCEpTION as a flexible and resourceful tool. Through ARIADNEplus’ VREs, users have in turn an easy and free access to a web service, enabling them to work and collaborate on their NLP projects in an efficient way and without the linguistic and computer science knowledge required to manually craft entities-matching rules.

10.8 Deviation from the work plan

After a short delay linked with the availability of the NLP ARIADNEplus service, no deviation from the work plan occurred.

⁵⁴ INCEpTION accepts the following input formats: CoNLL 2000, CoNLL 2002, CoNLL 2003, CoNLL 2006, CoNLL 2009, CoNLL 2012, CoNLL CoreNLP, CoNLL-U, Corpus Workbench Format (VRT), HTML, HTML (legacy), LAPPS Interchange Format, NLP Interchange Format (NIF), PDF, Perseus Treebank XML (2.1), plain text, plain text (one sentence per line), plain text (space-separated tokens, one sentence per line), PubAnnotation Documents with Section (JSON), TEI, UIMA CAS XMI (XML 1.0), UIMA CAS XMI (XML 1.1), UIMA Binary CAS, WebAnno TSV v1 (WebAnno v1.x), WebAnno TSV v2 (WebAnno v2.x), WebAnno TSV v3.3 (WebAnno v3.x), WebLicht TCF, XML (generic).

⁵⁵ INCEpTION accepts the following output formats: CoNLL 2000, CoNLL 2002, CoNLL 2003, CoNLL 2006, CoNLL 2009, CoNLL 2012, CoNLL CoreNLP, CoNLL-U, Inline XML, LAPPS Interchange Format, NLP Interchange Format (NIF), plain text, TEI, UIMA CAS JSON, UIMA CAS XMI (XML 1.0), UIMA CAS XMI (XML 1.1), UIMA Binary CAS, WebAnno TSV v3.3 (WebAnno v3.x), WebLicht TCF, XML (generic).

11 Conclusions

The WP aimed to test the infrastructure and its services in concrete cases of use by the archaeological community. The goal was to provide tested operational tools for archaeologists. The dependence of the development of the pilots on the implementation of the services may have contributed to different speeds of implementation. Nevertheless, the conclusion at the end of the WP shows the richness of the experiments. Each one demonstrates in its own field of application the multiple facets of the added value of the project for the European archaeological communities. Thus, the cross-fertilization network that ARIADNEplus represents is an immense and undefined space for knowledge exploration. The infrastructure brings new knowledge to very specific areas. Beyond that, the pilots demonstrate the power of the infrastructure to expose new data, sometimes from complex formats (e.g., 3D, GIS). Finally, the development of services around the data repository provides the user with powerful and accessible tools to test and develop new methods of knowledge exploration.